

EMIRATES SOCIAL IMPACT ASSESMENT

AUTHORS:

- Attivor Novisi (1027132)
- Annovati Chiara (958102)
- Gill Navraaj Kaur (1027455)

ABOUT THE COMPANY

EMIRATES IS A GLOBAL AIRLINE, SERVING 148 AIRPORTS IN 79 COUNTRIES FROM ITS HUB IN DUBAI, UNITED ARAB EMIRATES. DNATA IS ONE OF THE WORLD'S LARGEST COMBINED AIR SERVICES PROVIDERS IN THE WORLD, SERVING 173 CITIES AND AIRPORTS IN 35 COUNTRIES. ITS MAIN ACTIVITIES ARE THE PROVISION OF CARGO AND GROUND HANDLING, CATERING, AND TRAVEL SERVICES

الإمارات
Emirates

CAPITALS

HUMAN CAPITAL

To support our expanding operations as well as our future requirements, we welcomed 17,160 new employees, taking our workforce strength to 102,379 by 31 March.

24,383 employee recognitions worth AED 5.2 million in 2022-23:

- 15,879 Najms conferred worth AED 1.2 million
- 7,815 Shukrans shared worth AED 600,000
- 689 employees received Long Service Awards worth AED 3.4 million

PEOPLE DEVELOPMENT IN 2022-2023

64,760 - 19% increase Employees completed online courses

398 - 825% increase Employees in executive development programmes

EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANNING TRAINING AND EXERCISES

This year, nearly 24,500 operational employees trained on our safety management system and nearly 17,000 on emergency response planning in case of aircraft incidents.

Emirates has ranked consistently high in the industry's safety standards. Nearly 24,500 operational employees – from pilots to engineers – were trained about our safety management system through the year.

Through the year, nearly 17,000 employees were trained online or in instructor-led courses on emergency response planning. Of these, 240 were trained in emcare – the team activated to offer humanitarian and logistical support to customers, crew, and their loved ones in the event of an accident, serious incident or medical event.

- 16,426 employees Ground operation
- 256 employees At Emirates Group Headquarters
- 240 employees emcare

MANUFACTURING CAPITAL

Average fleet age in months

Fleet information						
Aircraft	Total as at 31 March 2023	Owned*	Leased	Total as at 31 March 2022	Change since 31 March 2022	Future deliveries
A 380-800	116	61	55	118	(2)	-
B 777-300ER	123	66	57	124	(1)	-
B 777-200LR	10	6	4	10	-	-
B 787-9	-	-	-	-	-	30
B 777-X	-	-	-	-	-	115
A 350-900	-	-	-	-	-	50
Passenger	249	133	116	252	(3)	195
B777 Freighters	11	2	9	10	1	5
Freighters	11	2	9	10	1	5
Total aircraft	260	135	125	262	(2)	200

*Includes aircraft acquired on secured financing.

AIRCRAFT DEPARTURES

* in thousands

*includes both passenger and cargo flights

PASSENGER NUMBERS IN MILLIONS

FINANCIAL CAPITAL

We offered multiple scholarship programmes to high-school graduates to complete their undergraduate degrees and obtain special licenses.

Programmes include:

- National Cadet Pilot Programme
- Aircraft Maintenance Engineer License (AMEL) Scholarship Programme
- Aviation Management Programme
- The Technologist Programme
- Finance Scholarship Programme:

REVENUE TREND IN AED BN

REVENUE COMPOSITION

NON-TRANSPORT REVENUE

GEOGRAPHICAL REVENUE

COST COMPOSITION

LIABILITIES IN AED BN

ORGANIZATIONAL CAPITAL

- 1,200+ check-in and boarding agents ab initio training at Emirates Terminal 3
- 380 sales professionals and managers from 60 countries
- 24 new workshops to 2,000+ people in-class and online across 64 countries
- 19,000 employees completed Environment course
- 26,000 employees completed Autism course
- 567 HR professionals completed 6,538 learning items on D&I training

Emirates policies provide guidance to their employees, partners, and suppliers, stating the standards, behaviours and actions expected of them, and of our organisation. These policies are made available to relevant stakeholders and are regularly reviewed and communicated.

Systems and programmes are put in place to ensure awareness and compliance.

- Anti-bribery & corruption policy
- Anti-slavery and human trafficking policy
- Antitrust and competition policy
- Anti-money laundering policy
- Sanctions & export controls policy
- Conflicts of interest policy
- Employee code of conduct
- Data privacy policies
- Cybersecurity policies

Safety Management System training in numbers

- flight crew → 3514
- cabin crew → 14454
- senior manager → 13
- engineering → 3070
- ground operations → 3234
- safety risk assessment workshop → 132

NATURAL CAPITAL

In the UAE's Year of Sustainability, the Emirates Group signed up to the United Nations Global Compact, a voluntary global initiative that promotes responsible business practices and the advancement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Notable environmental highlights for 2022-23 include: Emirates' successful demonstration flight using 100% sustainable aviation fuel (SAF).

Operational fuel efficiency: Under the governance of a cross-functional Operations Efficiency Steering Group, we actively implement ways to reduce unnecessary fuel burn and emissions, while maintaining the highest safety standards.

Emirates has taken a significant step forward with the successful implementation of Green Standard Operating Procedures (Green SOPs) by our pilots, a result of a multi-faceted approach involving education, awareness, data analytics and technology. Our Green SOPs include measures such as: using reduced engine taxi, idle reverse, prudent judgement on extra fuel, optimised flap landing, inflight speed management to minimise fuel burn, and use of direct routing opportunities. In 2022-23, Green SOPs and other operating initiatives helped to reduce fuel burn by more than 50,000 tonnes and carbon emissions by over 160,000 tonnes.

Renewable energy: We have invested in solar power systems to generate clean electricity at our major facilities. In Dubai, this includes the Emirates Engine Maintenance Centre, Emirates Flight Catering, the Emirates Sevens Stadium, and our new pilot training centre, which will open in 2024. Our current installations generate over 9,000 MWh of renewable electricity annually, saving about 4 million kilogrammes of carbon dioxide emissions.

In 2022-23, we recycled more than 500,000 kilograms of plastic and glass from our flights arriving in Dubai. Cabin crew segregate used plastic and glass bottles from our flights, and in collaboration with Emirates Flight Catering, these items are sent to a recycling plant in Dubai.

INPUT

OUTPUT

OUTCOME

HUMAN CAPITAL

- Emirates has 105,730 employees.
- 41% of Emirates employees are women, while 59% are men.
- The most common ethnicity at Emirates is White (39%).
- 19% of Emirates employees are Asian.
- The most common age range of Emirates employees is 20-30 years. 62% of Emirates employees are between the ages of 20-30 years.
- A plurality of employees at Emirates stay for 1-2 years. 35% of Emirates employees stay at the company for 1-2 years.

Community engagement:

- Dnata4good;
- Emirates Airline Foundation;
- Disaster and humanitarian relief.

People development:

- Reward and recognition;
- Learning and training;
- Internship programmes.

Women:

- Pay equity;
- Record promotions for women;
- More learning and development opportunities for women;
- IATA [25by2025](#) pledge.

([25by2025](#): pledge that by 2025 signatories will either increase their proportion of women in senior positions to 25% or achieve a 25% increase in that metric.)

IMPACT

SDG 4:

- Provides cabin crew and ground staff with training on necessary skills for their job and future career;
- Emirates helps shine a spotlight on the issue of human trafficking.

SDGs 5/10:

- UAE gender balance pledge;
- Access to world-class training for women;
- Emirates will continue to facilitate women flying in aviation;
- Community service through humanitarian action.

SDGs

4 QUALITY
EDUCATION

5 GENDER
EQUALITY

10 REDUCED
INEQUALITIES

INPUT

MANUFACTURING CAPITAL

OUTPUT

Our pilots are empowered with the latest technology and tools to monitor and review their flight performance, improving their awareness of how their flying techniques impact fuel consumption and carbon emissions.

The Emirates Group and Dubai Future Foundation partner to launch the Emirates Centre of Excellence for Aviation Robotics. The Centre provides a dedicated R&D platform for top global talent as well as local students to engage in solving complex challenges in the aviation industry using advanced science and technologies

To enable a culture around people development, we're investing nearly AED 50 million on a suite of programmes: executive coaching, online and classroom training, technical and non-technical courses, workshops, and mentoring.

OUTCOME

Aircraft fleet strategy:

Operating modern and fuel-efficient aircraft has always been central to Emirates' business model. They fly one of the youngest wide-body aircraft fleets with an average age of 9.1 years, considerably lower than the industry average. Their new-generation Airbus A350 and Boeing aircraft will also provide greater fuel efficiency as they join our fleet starting 2024 and 2025 respectively.

Unlocking global supply chains:

Emirates reaffirmed its commitment to cargo customers and its confidence in global trade flows by announcing a firm order for 5 new Boeing 777Fs, worth over US\$ 1.7 billion at list prices. Two of these aircraft will enter SkyCargo's fleet in 2024 and the remaining 3 in 2025. With 2 new Boeing 777Fs joining the fleet, and having retired one older freighter, Emirates SkyCargo's 11 777Fs crisscrossed the globe to 150, including 9 freighter-only, destinations.

IMPACT

SDG 8:

- UAE National development;
- Best technology adopted to maximize profits/growth.

SDG 11:

- Modern aircrafts;
- Sustainable aviation fuel;
- Water conservation on vehicles;
- Renewable energy on all manufacturing capital;
- Sustainable procureme

SDGs

8 DECENT WORK AND
ECONOMIC GROWTH

10 REDUCED
INEQUALITIES

11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES
AND COMMUNITIES

INPUT

FINANCIAL CAPITAL

OUTPUT

Emirates's annual revenue is \$16.7B.

Emirates has 105,730 employees, and the revenue per employee ratio is \$157,949.

Emirates peak revenue was \$16.7B in 2022.

Emirates Salary Estimate \$47,072
\$22.63 hourly rate

Entry-Level Salary \$22,000 yearly salary

OUTCOME

Future Revenues:

Emirates reports its most profitable year ever with a profit of AED 10.6 billion (US\$ 2.9 billion) compared with AED 3.9 billion (US\$ 1.1 billion) loss in the previous year.

By this information we can logically expect a positive growth in the revenue of the company for, at least, the next 6-12 months.

Future Expenses:

What we expect from the Emirates Group, given all the promises and actions made towards a green future, we can logically expect expenses to be quite high in the next few years in preparation for a cheaper future.

DISCLAIMER: predictions made on future revenues/expenses are not very liable due to the nature of the subject

IMPACT

SDG 8:

- UAE National development

Emirates group has seen an economic growth of 1467% over the last 22 years and is well set to keep growing, especially after the revival of the aviation industry post-pandemic.

SDG 5:

- Achieving competent salaries for women;
- Glass ceiling reduction/cancellation

SDGs

8 DECENT WORK AND
ECONOMIC GROWTH

5 GENDER
EQUALITY

INPUT

OUTPUT

OUTCOME

ORGANIZATIONAL CAPITAL

Staff training:

Ab initio training (+ e-learning)

Group medical training (ex: First aid skills, how to deal with invisible disabilities, etc.)

Security training

Cabin service

Image and uniform

Duty-free sales

Recurrent training

Pilots training: Emirates Flight Training Academy

Emirates Group provides scholarship and career opportunities for Emirati high school graduates;

Business ethics:

- Code of conduct;
- Conflicts of interest policy;
- Whistleblower programme;
- Anti-bribery & corruption policy;
- Anti-slavery and human trafficking policy.

Supply chain management:

- Supplier code of conduct.

Regulatory compliance:

- Audits and certifications;
- Anti-money laundering policy;
- Antitrust and competition policy;
- Financial transparency;
- Data privacy policies;
- Cybersecurity policies;
- Safety policy and programmes;
- Sanctions & export controls policy;
- Applicable environmental regulations.

IMPACT

SDG 4:

- Provides cabin crew and ground staff with training on necessary skills for their job and future career;
- Product and service monitoring, leading to a better service.

SDG 17:

- Sponsorships;
- Start-up ecosystems;
- Developing pipeline of aviators;
- Building new schools and universities;
- Suppliers and partnerships sustainable procurement.

SDG 3:

- Employee well-being initiatives and monitoring.

SDGs

INPUT

OUTPUT

OUTCOME

NATURAL CAPITAL

- Electricity consumption MWh 395,978
- Renewable electricity generated (solar) MWh 9,214
- Water consumption ML 3,095
- Waste diverted from disposal tonnes 13,986
- CO2 emissions tonnes 26,966,466
- Energy consumption TJ 373,958

Renewable energy:

We have invested in solar power systems to generate clean electricity at our major facilities. In Dubai, this includes the Emirates Engine Maintenance Centre, Emirates Flight Catering, the Emirates Sevens Stadium, and our new pilot training centre, which will open in 2024. Our current installations generate over 9,000 MWh of renewable electricity annually, saving about 4 million kilogrammes of carbon dioxide emissions.

Operational fuel efficiency:

Under the governance of a cross-functional Operations Efficiency Steering Group, they actively implement ways to reduce unnecessary fuel burn and emissions, while maintaining safety standards.

IMPACT

SDGs 7/11/13:

- Renewable energy;
- Modern aircrafts;
- Efficient operations;
- Sustainable aviation fuel.

SDGs 12/13:

- Regulatory policy on sustainability;
- Waste minimisation;
- Water conservation;
- Recycling;
- Reach net zero carbon emissions by 2050.

SDG 13:

- Anti-wildlife trafficking;
- Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve.

SDGs

SPECIFIC IMPACT INDICATORS

SDGs

Goal 4 - Provide quality, equitable and inclusive education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all

indicator

4.1 By 2030, provide internship opportunities for all students ensuring they are equipped with the right training and skills for employment and decent jobs.

4.2 - By 2030, substantially increase the number of youth and adults who have the necessary skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs, and entrepreneurial skills

4.3 By 2030, ensure that every employee has received quality education and training specifically in areas such as Engineering, air traffic management and pilot training.

4.4 By 2030, create opportunities where disadvantaged children, youths and adults can have access to quality education by funding schools, learning programmes, and building entire campuses with classrooms, dormitories, sports fields, libraries and computer laboratories.

**Standard sub-
indicator**

4.1.1 Percentage of students participating in internship programs offered by the Emirates Group. Percentage of internships aligned with students' fields of study relevant to the aviation and travel industry. Measurement of employability skills acquired during internships with the Emirates Group.

4.2.2 Total number of youth and adults participating in skills development and training programs offered by the Emirates group. Percentage of skills programs aligned with the aviation and travel industry's needs. Percentage of participants who successfully complete the skills development programs.

4.3.3 Percentage of employees who have received training in their specific areas of expertise, including engineering, air traffic management, and pilot training. Assessment of the relevance of training programs to the specific needs of the aviation and travel industry. Number of employees participating in ongoing education and professional development programs.

4.4 The total number of schools funded by the Emirates Group.: Percentage of disadvantaged children, youths, and adults enrolled in learning programs supported by the Emirates Group. Number of entire campuses developed, including classrooms, dormitories, sports fields, libraries, and computer laboratories. Assessment of the accessibility of educational opportunities for disadvantaged children, youths, and adults.

SDGs

Goal 5 - Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls

indicator

5.1– Substantially increase the number of women working in technical areas such as engineering and flight crew.

5.2 - Increase the use of enabling technologies, particularly information and communication technologies, to promote women's empowerment.

5.3 By 2030, ensure that UAE gender balance pledge has been fully fulfilled (The pledge includes four pillars ; ensuring equal pay, promoting recruitment and promotion on the basis of gender equality, including in senior leadership positions, mainstreaming a gender balance perspective in policies and programs governing work in companies to support employees, and finally being transparent and providing the UAE GBC between the gender steps achieved in each company joined the undertaking)

Standard sub-indicator

5.1.1 – - Proportion of women in technical positions. (Women in technical bodies)

5.2.2 Percentage of women with access to and regular use of ICT tools (e.g., smartphones, computers, internet)
Percentage of women participating in online forums, social media, and other digital platforms.

5.3.3 Percentage of women in leadership positions (e.g., board members, executive roles). Gender pay gap analysis, comparing the average earnings of male and female employees in similar roles. Percentage of women in the total workforce. Implementation of policies promoting gender inclusivity. Percentage of women in decision-making bodies and committees. Participation rates in training and development programs, disaggregated by gender.

Measurement instrument

Workforce gender diversity

Gender responsive training programs

Gender pays gap, representations in leadership positions and gender inclusive recruitment practices

SDGs

Goal 7 - Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy systems for all

indicator

7.1- By 2030, significantly increase the number of modern and fuel-efficient aircraft.

7.2 By 2030, reduce unnecessary fuel burn and emissions, while maintaining the highest safety standards.

7.3 Support initiatives that contribute to the deployment of SAF and actively engage with the rapidly developing SAF industry.

7.4 By 2030, ensure that solar power systems that generate clean energy are installed in all Emirates facilities.

Standard sub-indicator

7.1.1 Percentage of the Emirates Group's fleet composed of modern and fuel-efficient aircraft. Number of new modern and fuel-efficient aircraft purchased by the Emirates Group.: Improvement in fuel efficiency ratings across the Emirates Group's fleet. Progress toward meeting emissions reduction targets set by the Emirates Group.

7.2.2- Percentage improvement in fuel efficiency across the Emirates Group's operations. Progress toward meeting specific emission reduction targets set by the Emirates Group. Progress toward meeting specific emission reduction targets set by the Emirates Group.

7.3.3 Percentage of Sustainable Aviation Fuel used in the Emirates Group's total fuel consumption. Progress toward meeting specific targets for procuring Sustainable Aviation Fuel. Number of partnerships and collaborations established with organizations in the Sustainable Aviation Fuel industry.

7.4 Percentage of Emirates Group facilities equipped with installed solar power systems. Total installed solar capacity in megawatts (MW) across all Emirates Group facilities. Percentage of total energy consumption derived from solar power systems. Allocation of investment towards the installation and maintenance of solar power systems.

Measurement instrument

Renewable energy adoption

Investment in Clean Energy Technologies

Carbon Emission Reduction

Adoption of Sustainable Aviation Fuel

SDGs

Goal 8 - Fostering economic, lasting, inclusive and sustainable growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all

indicator

8.1 - Achieve higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading and innovation, including leveraging high value-added and labor-intensive departments in Emirates.

8.2 Provide skilled and often high-value employment opportunities for women and men, including youth and people with disabilities, and ensure equal pay for work of equal value.

8.3 Prioritize the well-being of employees by offering health and wellness programs, mental health support, and a conducive work environment. This can contribute to increased job satisfaction and productivity.

8.4. Collaborate with industry stakeholders, government agencies, and non-governmental organizations to address challenges related to sustainable economic growth and employment in the aviation and travel sector.

8.5 - Protect labor rights and promote a safe and secure work environment for all workers, including migrant workers, especially migrant women, and precarious workers.

8.6 Regularly assess and audit subcontractors and suppliers to ensure they adhere to labor rights standards.

Standard sub-indicator

8.1.1 - Annual growth rate of real GDP per person employed (Annual growth rate of real GDP per person employed - Annual growth rate of volume value added per person employed - Annual growth rate of volume value added per hour worked)

8.2.2 Percentage of women in skilled and high-value employment positions within the Emirates Group. Percentage of women in skilled and high-value employment positions within the Emirates Group. Percentage of employees with disabilities in the workforce.

8.3.3 Percentage of employees participating in health and wellness programs. Accessibility and utilization rates of mental health support services. Results of regular workplace satisfaction surveys. Monitoring and reporting of employee stress levels every 3 months.

8.4.4 Number of collaborative initiatives with industry stakeholders, government agencies, and NGOs. Frequency of participation in industry forums and working groups. Number of instances where the company advocates for policies supporting sustainable economic growth and employment.

8.5 - Number of fatal and non-fatal injuries per 100,000 workers, by sex and migrant status.

8.5 - National level of compliance with labor rights (freedom of association and collective bargaining) according to International Labor Organization (ILO) textual sources and national legislation, by sex and migrant status

8.6.6 Percentage of subcontractors and suppliers adhering to labor right standards

**Measurement
instrument**

Labor Productivity

Employment Rates

Access to Healthcare and Well-being Programs,

Formalization of Employment Contracts:

SDGs

Goal 10 - Reduce inequalities between and within countries

indicator

10.1 Provide equal access to training and development opportunities to enhance the skills and capabilities of all employees.

10.2. Implement fair and transparent compensation policies to reduce income inequality within the company.

10.4 Implement measures to address gender pay gaps and actively work towards increasing the representation of women in leadership roles

10.5 Ensure facilities, services and employment opportunities are accessible and inclusive for persons with disabilities.

10.3 Implement and communicate policies that promote diversity, inclusion, and equal opportunities for all employees

Standard sub-indicator

10.1 Number of training hours provided per employee, disaggregated by employee category.

10.2. Ratio of the average income of the top 10% to the bottom 10% of employees.

10.4 Gender pay gap analysis, comparing the average earnings of male and female employees in similar roles.

Percentage of women in leadership positions

10.5 Number of facilities and services with improved accessibility features for persons with disabilities.

Percentage of employees who have access to professional development and career advancement opportunities, disaggregated by gender and other relevant factors.

SDGs

Goal 11 - Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable

indicator

11.1 Regularly assess and improve accessibility features, including infrastructure and services, to ensure inclusivity for persons with disabilities.

11.2 Implement fuel-efficient technologies, invest in sustainable aviation fuels, and monitor and report on emission reductions.

11.3 Develop and implement plans to respond to and recover from potential disasters, ensuring the resilience of operations and communities.

11.4 Implement and improve waste management practices, including recycling initiatives and reduction of single-use plastics.

Standard sub-indicator

11.1.1 Number of accessibility features implemented in airports and aircraft

11.2.2 Percentage reduction in the carbon footprint per passenger-kilometer

11.3.3 Completion and regular testing of disaster response and recovery plans

11.4.4 Percentage of waste recycled or diverted from landfills

SDGs

Goal 12 - Ensure sustainable patterns of production and consumption.

indicator

12.2 - By 2030, achieve sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources.

12.3 - Implement waste reduction strategies, enhance recycling programs, and minimize single-use plastics.

12.5 - By 2030, substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse.

12.6 - Implement water conservation measures, invest in water-efficient technologies, and monitor water usage across operations.

Standard sub-indicator

12.2.1 - Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint on GDP

12.2.2 - Domestic material consumption, domestic material consumption per capita, and domestic material consumption per unit of GDP

12.3.1 - Increase in the percentage of waste recycled and decrease in the overall waste generated.

12.5.1 - Domestic recycling rate, tons of material recycled.

12.6.1 Reduction in water consumption per passenger or per unit of production.

SDGs

Goal 13 - Take urgent measures to combat climate change and its consequences

indicator

13.3 Educate employees about climate change, its impacts, and the company's initiatives to address it, fostering a culture of sustainability

Standard sub-indicator

13.3.1 Number of employees participating in climate awareness and training programs.

SDGs

Goal 16 - Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development; make access to justice available for all and create effective, accountable and inclusive bodies at all levels

indicator

16.6- Regularly assess and report on legal compliance, including adherence to aviation regulations and labor laws.

16.7 - Ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms, in accordance with national legislation and international agreements

16.8 Establish effective mechanisms for customers to address complaints and disputes, ensuring fair and accessible processes.

Standard sub-indicator

16.6.1 Level of compliance with national and international laws and regulations.

16.7- Number of countries that adopt and implement constitutional, legal and/or policy guarantees for public access to information.

16.8 - Timeliness and effectiveness of mechanisms for addressing customer complaints and disputes.

THANK YOU!

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